

PRINCIPLES OF ACCOUNTING – QUICK CASES

UNIT 1: CASE 1. ECOBUILD

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CASE OUTLINE

Scenario: EcoBuild Ltd. is a one-year-old start-up that produces modular, eco-friendly houses and positions itself as a socially responsible company. The founder and director, Mr. Adam Brain, is an architect with 15 years of experience in sustainable construction. His passion lies in design and innovation, not finance.

The Problem:

While EcoBuild's financial reporting is sound, its environmental reporting and supply chain compliance monitoring are weak. Mr. Brain requires reliable, non-financial data to manage the company's sustainability objectives, specifically the trade-offs between cost and benefit and between short-term profit and long-term sustainability.

Current Financial Position:

- annual turnover: €1,200,000 (revenue recognised from pilot contracts).
- net loss: €100,000 in the first year.
- investment: € 600,000 from private investors.

Risks:

Potential accusation of "greenwashing" and loss of investor trust due to the inability to substantiate sustainability claims with non-financial Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Critical cash flow shortage: the company has tied up all capital in raw materials for new orders but lacks the liquidity to pay operating expenses due to poor planning and cash collection.

The Challenge:

The purchasing manager presents two material options for a new large contract:

1. **Eco-certified wood:** high quality, sustainable, but 20% more expensive.
2. **Standard wood:** cheaper, immediately available, but linked to suppliers with weak environmental practices.

Mr. Brain is tempted by the cheaper option to improve short-term profitability, but this choice directly contradicts EcoBuild's mission and commitment to sustainability.

Your Task as an Intern at EcoBuild:

Your role is to help Mr. Brain implement necessary changes. You must outline and recommend the first two or three steps that EcoBuild should take to establish a reliable sustainability reporting system that aligns its financial accounting with its eco-mission. This implementation plan should focus on how the company can measure, track, and report non-financial data to ensure transparency and trust.

CASE RESOURCES

Core Resource

Smith, S. (2024). The evolving role of accountants. Unit 1 in Smith, S., Murphy, R., and Rose, J. *Principles of Accounting*. Available at: <http://www.accounting-streams.org/principles-of-accounting/01.html>.

Focus: Section 1.3: Defining accounting as a technical, social, and moral practice

Optional Resources for Extended Discussion

Carnegie, G. (2022). Accounting 101: Redefining accounting for tomorrow. *Accounting Education*, 31(6), 615-628. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/citedby/10.1080/09639284.2021.2014915>

Alternative Resources (Focusing on Sustainability Tensions):

For General Discussion

Aliyu, S. and York, T. (2024). 'Sustainability accounting is coming: here's how to navigate it', *Times Higher Education*, 1 February. Available at: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/sustainability-accounting-coming-heres-how-navigate-it>

For a More Advanced Discussion (Addressing Materiality and Tension)

Jørgensen, S., Mjøs, A. and Pedersen, L.J.T. (2022) 'Sustainability reporting and approaches to materiality: tensions and potential resolutions', *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*, 13(2), pp. 341-361. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAMPJ-01-2021-0009>

CASE QUESTIONS AND DISCUSSION

You are an intern at EcoBuild Ltd. Your goal is to help the Director, Mr. Adam Brain, align the company's financial practices with its environmental mission.

Explain to Mr. Brain how viewing accounting as more than just 'numbers' (a social and moral tool) can benefit the company's reputation.

Objective: Synthesise your analysis by addressing these four key areas:

1. Dimensions of Accounting: Briefly explain how adopting a technical, social, and moral view of accounting can help EcoBuild achieve its environmental mission.
2. Moral Dilemma: From a moral perspective, what should guide your decision regarding eco-certified vs. standard materials, considering both profit and long-term reputation?

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3. Stakeholder Needs: Identify the key stakeholders (e.g., investors, community) and explain what information they need to trust EcoBuild's sustainability claims.
 4. Action Plan: What are the first three practical steps EcoBuild should take to establish a reporting system that integrates financial and environmental data, specifically identifying non-financial Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (e.g., percentage of eco-certified wood used, carbon footprint per house) to substantiate sustainability claims and ensure transparency?